

Exploring Safe Reinforcement Learning Using Safety Shields Derived With System-Theoretic Process Analysis: A Case-Study on a Cruise Ship Hotel System

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Abstract—The cruise ship industry is under increasing pressure to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, as international regulations define ambitious requirements and goals for modern cruise ships. One of the most significant consumers of energy onboard cruise ships are their Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. However, the energy optimization of HVAC systems is challenging, as they are impacted by a number of uncontrolled variables, such as changing weather conditions, passenger behavior, and the demands of other significant energy consumers, such as propulsion systems. Reinforcement Learning (RL) is often used to tackle such complex optimization tasks, however concerns over ensuring the safety of RL optimized systems hinders its adoption in industry, especially in the context of safety-critical systems. This paper presents the initial findings of applying a novel approach to ensure safety in RL: a safety shield developed utilizing a novel hazard analysis method, System-Theoretic Process Analysis. In this work the safety shield is used to both train the RL agent as well as block unsafe behavior in operation. Preliminary findings suggest that blocking unsafe behavior during training hinders the ability to learn a safe RL policy, however, when used in testing the approach is capable of significantly reducing the number of safety violations.

Index Terms—STPA, RL, cruise ships, energy optimization, safety shield

I. INTRODUCTION

Reducing the environmental impact of the maritime industry is becoming increasingly important. The pressure to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is reflected by the International Maritime Organization’s 2023 Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships, which defines a transition to zero GHG emissions in accordance with the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals [1]. One of the key means to achieve the ambitious sustainability goals in the cruise ship industry is energy optimization [2].

A promising approach to solving complex energy optimization problems is Reinforcement Learning (RL) [3]. RL defines optimization goals through rewards that it must maximize. Research on its application for energy optimization has been conducted for a variety of use cases such as building energy optimization [4], the optimization of propulsion systems in ships [5], and ship route optimization [6]. While RL is a promising solution to the energy optimization needs of the

maritime industry, it comes with its own set of challenges. Ensuring the safety of a system that incorporates RL into its control scheme is a notable concern hindering industry adoption of the method [7].

One method to ensuring the safety of RL based systems is to construct a safety shield. Different approaches to implementing a safety shield have been suggested, many of which suggest the safety shield should block actions which exceed a certain threshold for the probability of an unsafe state being reached [8] [9]. These approaches have shown promise on simple examples with games like PAC-MAN and Snake, however, their application to more complex systems is yet to be explored. In this context probabilities may be hard to estimate, and actions which lead to hazardous states as well as the hazardous states themselves may be challenging to define.

System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) is a novel hazard analysis method capable of identifying hazards caused by unintended interactions between system components as well as the context in which interactions become hazardous. This paper proposes a novel approach to ensuring the safety of RL based energy optimization by utilizing STPA, which is performed on a cruise ship hotel HVAC system. The results of the analysis are used to construct a safety shield and training environment for the RL agent. The safety shield is used to monitor and penalize potentially hazardous actions and system states, as well as block actions that could lead to such states. The intended outcome is twofold: the RL algorithm should reach a safe policy over the course of a number of training episodes, and the safety shield will continue to block actions it predicts to be unsafe when the RL agent has finished training and is implemented in a system.

II. BACKGROUND

A. System-Theoretic Process Analysis

System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) is a hazard analysis method based on the System-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes (STAMP) [10]. In STAMP, systems are modeled as hierarchical “control structures” in which system elements on higher levels of the control structure assert control over elements on the lower levels of the control structure. Elements

on lower levels in turn provide feedback to elements on higher levels. The model considers accidents as the result of inadequate or inappropriate control between the elements in the control structure [11]. An example of such a control structure is given in Figure 1.

STPA adds to the STAMP model, by providing a method by which the model can be systematically analyzed. It consists of four steps: defining the purpose and scope of the analysis, modeling the control structure, determining unsafe control actions (UCAs), and generating loss scenarios [10]. The outcomes of each step are utilized in the steps that follow, and are also valuable results of the analysis in themselves. These steps will be briefly explored in this section, as well as how they relate to the use case explored in this work.

Step 1 of the STPA analysis defines the losses, hazards, system-level safety constraints, and the boundaries of the system being analyzed. Losses are outcomes that are to be prevented, such as loss of life, property damage, loss of revenue, etc. System states that may lead to a loss are referred to as hazards. In an air conditioning system such as the one explored in this work, a system hazard may be a high carbon dioxide content or low temperature in a cabin.

In Step 2 of the STPA analysis, a hierarchical control structure of the system is determined. This control structure defines controllers and controlled processes in the system, and the control actions and feedback that formalize the interactions between the controllers and controlled processes.

Step 3 in turn consists of deriving unsafe control actions (UCAs) from the control actions identified in Step 2. UCAs document type of UCA and the context in which control actions become unsafe. The types of UCAs are guided by the key words: not provided, provided, provided for incorrect duration, provided at the wrong time. The context may refer to an operational condition, for example when a cruise ship is in rough seas, or a system is undergoing maintenance.

Crucially to this work Step 3 of the analysis also identifies controller constraints, which are, in essence, negations of the UCAs identified for each controller. Violating these constraints could lead to a hazardous state in the system, therefore a controller — such as the one proposed in this paper — should adhere to these constraints to ensure that it operates in a safe manner.

B. Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) refers to methods in which an agent learns to navigate a state space by maximizing a reward signal. This reward signal is determined by a reward function designed for each use case specifically and reflects the desired behavior of the agent. The behavior of the RL agent is guided by its policy. This policy is adjusted according to the reward that the RL agent collects over the course of each training episode. Usually, over the course of hundreds of training episodes the policy of the RL agent is improved such that it aligns with optimization goal. In this work, we use a Penalized Proximal Policy Optimization (P3O) approach for

the RL agent, which introduces a separate cost function in addition to the reward function.

C. Cruise ship hotel systems

Hotel systems in cruise ships consists of a large number of subsystems, for example different entertainment systems, laundry systems and fresh water systems. However, the air conditioning system is by far the most energy consuming of the hotel systems, often second in energy consumption to only the propulsion systems of the cruise ship [2]. The air conditioning system may account for up to 40% of the hotel load on a cruise ship.

The air conditioning system consists of air conditioning compressors, which produce cool water for air handling units (AHU) responsible for removing humidity, as well as cooling or heating the air. This air is then led to spaces such as cabins and atriums. Additionally, cabins often have their own fan coil units, which handle part of the temperature regulation demands of the cabin. Sometimes cabins also have variable air volume control, a system which enables the reduction of air flow to a cabin. [2]

III. METHODS

A. A partial STPA analysis

The analysis conducted in this work omitted the 4th step of STPA, as the results were not identified as supporting the development of a safety shield or the safety goals for the reward function generation. The partial STPA analysis was conducted for a general HVAC system with the addition of a "RL-Optimized Controller", which oversees and controls the components of the HVAC system through determining set-points and collecting sensor data such as cabin airflow, humidity, temperature, CO₂, and occupancy. The structure is best described by the Control Structure generated in Step 2 of the analysis, presented in Fig. 1. The Control Structure was refined iteratively with the feedback of a subject matter expert, who found the final Control Structure useful in describing the HVAC system for training purposes. The Control Structure was also found to be especially useful in developing the surrogate model used by both the shield and the RL agent.

B. Reward function generation and safety goals

The system-level safety constraints identified in Step 1 of the STPA analysis were used as natural language input for a reward function generation method utilizing Large Language Models [12] [13]. In addition, the optimization goals and environment description were used with the method to formulate the reward function for the Reinforcement Learning algorithm.

The parameters found in the system-level safety constraints are based on those provided in the ISO 7547:2022 standard [14], which defines design parameters for air-conditioning systems for accommodation spaces on cruise ships. While exceeding or falling short of the parameters does not pose an immediate threat to safety, the parameters allow the definition of a safe operational envelope for the HVAC system. The values may be considered arbitrary, however, the purpose is to

Fig. 1. The Control Structure diagram produced in the 2nd step of the STPA analysis, which demonstrates the proposed implementation of an RL-based Controller into a cruise ship HVAC system.

determine whether the RL agent can learn to operate within an operational envelope deemed safe.

TABLE I
SYSTEM-LEVEL SAFETY CONSTRAINTS.

SC-1.1	Cabin temperature must not exceed 25 degrees celsius.	H-1.1
SC-1.2	Cabin temperature must not fall below 22 degrees celsius.	H-1.2
SC-1.3	Cabin relative humidity must not exceed an average of 55 percent.	H-1.3
SC-1.4	Cabin relative humidity must not fall below 20 percent.	H-1.4
SC-1.5	Cabin air must not exceed carbon dioxide levels of 1000 ppm.	H-1.5
SC-2	Cabin must not have airflow during a fire in the cabin.	H-2

C. Formulating the safety shield

The safety shield is constructed using the controller constraints and system-level safety constraints defined in the STPA analysis. Although controller constraints are generally created using negations of UCAs, the number of constraints created in this analysis was significantly less than the number of UCAs generated, as the constraints define the only correct behavior allowed by the controller, whereas the UCAs outline multiple incorrect behaviors. The controller constraints are presented in Table II, however, the table excludes constraints C-8 and C-9, as they were not enforced by the shield due to limitations in the surrogate model.

The safety shield receives information about the current state of the system and the action suggested by the RL Agent from the training environment and the RL agent, respectively. Using a black-box surrogate model of the system, which is also used in the training environment to train the RL agent, the safety shield simulates the system several steps ahead with the action suggested by the RL agent and checks for violations.

If a violation occurs within a number of steps that is below the threshold, a new action is requested from the RL agent, and the safety shield repeats the simulation with the new action. Once an action is found that does not result in a violation within the specified number of steps, the action is allowed to be taken. If the RL agent cannot produce a safe action within a given number of attempts, the unsafe action is taken resulting in a violation.

TABLE II
CONTROLLER CONSTRAINTS.

C-1	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the AHU with a higher temperature setpoint if more than half of the cabins are below 22 degrees celsius.
C-2	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the AHU with a lower temperature setpoint if more than half of the cabins are above 25 degrees celsius.
C-3	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the AHU with a higher humidity setpoint if more than half of the cabins are below 20 percent relative humidity.
C-4	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the AHU with a lower humidity setpoint if more than half of the cabins are above 55 percent relative humidity.
C-5	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the VAV with a higher cabin airflow setpoint if the cabin CO2 levels exceed 1000 ppm.
C-6	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the VAV or FCU with a higher cabin temperature setpoint if the cabin temperature is below 22 degrees celsius.
C-7	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the VAV or FCU with a lower cabin temperature setpoint if the cabin temperature is over 25 degrees celsius.
C-10	The RL-Optimized Controller must provide the VAV with a cabin airflow setpoint that is above 8L/s/person under normal operating circumstances.

Fig. 2. The figure presents the moving average of safety violations over the course of training episodes, when unsafe actions are blocked by the shield and not blocked during the episodes. Each episode is 240 timesteps, and represents a day in the simulation model. The averaging window is 10 training episodes.

IV. RESULTS

While work is still ongoing, some interesting findings include how the shield affects the RL agent’s ability to learn a safe policy. Fig 2 presents a comparison of training episodes with unsafe actions blocked and not blocked. When the safety shield was utilized for blocking during training, the number of safety violations increased significantly over the course training episodes. In contrast, when only the cost function was utilized for learning safety, the number of violations decreased over the course of training episodes. This suggests that blocking unsafe actions during training hinders the RL agent’s ability to learn a safe policy, which aligns with findings in similar work on shielding RL agents [9].

When the safety shield is utilized in only testing the trained RL agent, it appears to significantly improve safety, however, some violations are still encountered. The number of potential violations is exaggerated in part due to defining safety through not only the system’s state (system-level safety constraints), but also the actions taken in states (controller constraints). The latter type of violations will be used in the ongoing work to penalize the agent during training.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary findings suggest that the approach is promising in balancing energy optimization and significantly reducing the unsafe behavior of trained RL agents. The results presented in this work indicate that simply blocking unsafe actions in training — without incurring a cost or reward — leads to significantly worse results, especially early in the training process. Additional experimentation with reward function generation, sampling new actions in cases where the safety shield blocks an action, and penalizing the agent for blocked actions in training are part of the ongoing work. The controller constraints and system-level safety constraints also provide a means for the safety shield to reward corrective action taken by the RL agent in a hazardous state. This should also be explored in future work.

Finally, it must be noted that the Control Structure provided indispensable utility in developing the surrogate model of the simulation and communicating with subject matter experts.

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